

Ethnic community membership

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

- 1) To which community do you feel part of?
- Kanak or Melanesian
 - European (born in New Caledonia or in Vanuatu)
 - European (born in France or elsewhere)
 - Wallisian, Futunian, Tahitian (Polynesian)
 - Indonesian, Vietnamese or Asian from another country
 - Other

Indicate to which extent you agree with the following statements.

	Not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
2) I spent time trying to learn more on my community group, such as its history, its traditions and customs.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3) I understand the meaning of belonging to a community group.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4) I understand the meaning of my community belonging and what it represents for me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5) I often did actions that helped me understand my community context.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6) To know more about my community background, I often spoke to other persons (family, friends or other).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7) I feel a strong attachment to my community group.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>